

PERCEPTION OF PAKISTANI NURSES REGARDING THEORY PRACTICE GAP IN NURSING PROFESSION

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Abstract

Background: The theory-practice gap is described as a lack of ability to relate and enforce the knowledge acquired in academics and research work with practice and its attending consequences make nurses vulnerable, thereby affecting the health care system of any nation in general

Objective: To assess the perception of Pakistani nurses regarding theory-practice gap in nursing profession

Methods: Descriptive study was conducted in the Tertiary Hospital of Lahore. Data was collected from the nurses with help of questionnaire. The data were analysed by using percentage, mean and standard deviation.

Results: In the present study majority of participants fall within the 21-30 age range, accounting for 87.8% of the total, the study includes 5.8% males and 94.2% females. Participants were also asked about their designation, with 13.5% identifying as instructors and 86.5% as clinicians. In terms of the highest level of education, 51.3% are general nurses, 42.3% hold a Bachelor's degree, and 6.4% have a Master's degree. In the present study showed that nurses with positive perception toward theory practice gap were 94%; however the number of nurses with negative perception were 5.8%.

Conclusion: study revealed that evidence based practice will improve student's , skill activity will improve students confident and skill acquisition after graduation thereby Furthermore the study analysis offers valuable insights into how Pakistani nurses perceive the relationship between theory and practice, providing a foundation for understanding their perspectives and potential areas for improvement within the profession. So the maximum nurses perceived that continuous education will help updating the nurses knowledge about the current technological advancement can help minimize the gap.

INTRODUCTION

The theory-practice gap is described as a lack of ability to relate and enforce the knowledge acquired in academics and research work with practice and its attending consequences make nurses vulnerable, thereby affecting the health care system of any nation in general. (1).The

theory-practice gap is concerning for the profession of nursing as its effects negatively decreased job satisfaction, increased job turnover rates, and increased patient-care errors (2). The theory-practice gap (TPG) has been a frequently identified construct in nursing education and

practice because the integration of theoretical content in practice does not usually occur smoothly (3). The two key elements of nursing education are theory and practice. While the practice environment dictates the circumstances in which the theoretical knowledge is applied, nursing theory serves as the foundation for nursing practice (4). The science of nursing is founded on applied research and is informed by theory that is supported by data. Many ideas within the field have emphasized both the theoretical sciences and the art of nursing (5).

The theory-practice gap, which affects nursing and midwifery as a whole, is the major problem facing nursing as an academic field. It is a "distancing of theoretical knowledge from the actual doing of practice," as it has been described and it affects both newly certified registered nurses beginning clinical practice and nursing students participating in clinical placements (6). Along with student and instructor elements in the teaching-learning environment, organizational culture and practices play a key role in the theory-practice divide. According to a number of research, the reasons for the gap's existence are complex (7).

Students and newly licensed nurses are primarily affected by the frustrations and challenges caused by the gap, which can hinder their socialization to the profession and subsequent professional development best summarized as the gap between the theories practitioners claim underlie their practice, and the implicit theories embedded within their practice, of which they may not be aware (8). Saleh in 2018 noted that the concept of theory-practice gap is common knowledge in nursing but has become the biggest challenge of the profession which is contributing to degrade the quality of service both in teaching and practice especially as newly qualified nurses reportedly find it at times extremely difficult to apply the knowledge they acquired during their education (7).

Numerous studies highlighted the value of having a sufficient supply of academic preceptors with appropriate training and clinical preceptors. Other methods to bridge the gap between theory and practice in nursing education have been discovered in these research such as the provision of explicit, context-based curricula (9).

The student nurses and newly qualified nurses encounter great difficulties associated with Theory-practice gap and this can have an adverse impact on

their professional role (9). Graduates often face incongruence between what was taught and what they actually face in the clinical area. This incongruence, graduate nurses who have theoretical knowledge but are not practically equipped to successfully apply their knowledge into practice is referred as the theory-practice gap (10). The theory-practice gap is concerning for the profession of nursing as its effects negatively impact patient safety. In addition, the deficit experienced by the new graduates contributes to decreased job satisfaction, increased job turnover rates, and increased patient-care errors. The existence of the Theory-practice gap has the ability to influence the provision of quality nursing care and patient outcomes. This article describes the experiences and perceptions of the Theory-practice gap in a resource-limited setting. The TPG has also been cited as a contributory factor in medication errors (11).

The theory-practice gap is a significant issue in nursing, impacting nurses' professional growth, job satisfaction, patient safety, and overall healthcare quality. This gap challenges the effective application of theoretical knowledge in practical settings, particularly for newly certified nurses and students during clinical placements. Contributing factors include teaching environments, organizational culture, and the lack of qualified preceptors. Addressing this gap requires collaborative efforts from educational institutions, healthcare organizations, and policymakers through context-based curricula and explicit educational strategies. This study examines Pakistani nurses' perceptions of the theory-practice gap, highlighting the need for improved integration to enhance nursing care, patient safety, and professional satisfaction.

Material & Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study design was used to collect data from a specific population at a single point in time at a tertiary hospital in Lahore, completed within four months post-approval of the synopsis. The sample size of 156 was determined using Taro Yamane's formula with a 92% confidence interval and an 8% margin of error, drawn from the hospital's nursing graduates. Convenient sampling was employed, and all nurses at the hospital with over two years of clinical experience who were willing to give informed consent were included, while nursing students and paramedical staff were excluded. Data collection used an adapted questionnaire (Hameed et al., 2023) comprising two parts: socio-demographic information and participants' perceptions of the theory-practice gap.

Following approval from the review committee, the purpose of the study was explained, and written consent was obtained to ensure ethical compliance and confidentiality. The questionnaire responses, finalized by the participants, were returned to the data collector

and subsequently analyzed using IBM SPSS software (version 26). Data analysis presented qualitative variables as frequencies and percentages, and quantitative variables as mean and standard deviation.

Results

Demographics		n	%
Age	21-30	137	87.8
	31-40	19	12.2
Gender	Male	9	5.8
	Female	147	94.2
What is your designation?	Instructor	21	13.5
	Clinician	135	86.5
What is your highest level of education?	General Nurse	80	51.3
	Bachelor	66	42.3
	Masters	10	6.4
What are your years of Experience?	3 years	39	25.0
	4-7 years	89	57.1
	8-10 years	19	12.2
	Above 10	9	5.8

Analyzed by frequency n and percentage %

Table 1 presents the demographic variables of the study participants, showing frequencies and percentages. Most participants (87.8%) are aged 21-30, with 12.2% aged 31-40. Gender distribution includes 5.8% males and 94.2% females. In terms of designation, 13.5% are instructors and 86.5% are clinicians. Educational levels include 51.3% general

nurses, 42.3% with a Bachelor's degree, and 6.4% with a Master's degree. Experience levels vary: 25.0% have 3 years, 57.1% have 4-7 years, 12.2% have 8-10 years, and 5.8% have over 10 years. Frequencies and percentages provide an overview of participants' demographic profile.

	Frequency	Percentage	X	SD
Score < 22 or <61%	9	5.8	28.39	3.994
Score > 22 or > 61 %	147	94.2		
Total	156	100.0		

Analyzed by frequency and percentage mean (X) and standard deviation (SD)

Table 2 shows that 94% of nurses (n=147) have a positive perception of the theory-practice gap in nursing, while 5.8% (n=9) hold a negative perception. The mean perception score was 28.39, with a standard deviation of 3.994.

Questions	N	Min	Max	X	SD
I think imploring evidence-based practice will improve my clinical judgment and invariably minimize the theory practice gap	156	1	4	3.31	0.752
I think using skill laboratory will improve students confident and skill acquisition after graduation thereby minimizing the theory practice gap	156	1	4	3.22	0.648
I think using nursing process in caring for the patient will help me improve my critical thinking ability and clinical judgment	156	1	4	3.26	0.610

Analyzed by mean (X) and Standard Deviation (SD)

Table 3 summarizes Pakistani nurses' perceptions of the theory-practice gap, detailing responses to questions on evidence-based practice, skill labs, and the nursing process. Key insights include high agreement that evidence-based practice improves clinical judgment (mean=3.31), skill labs enhance confidence and skills (mean=3.22), and applying the

nursing process bolsters critical thinking (mean=3.26). Data from 156 participants includes each question's minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation, underscoring a strong belief among nurses that evidence-based practice can significantly reduce the theory-practice gap.

Questions	N	Min	Max	X	SD
I think improving our interpersonal relationship and including habit of respecting other people's feeling, idea and input will help collaboration between clinicians and academicians	156	1	4	3.14	0.526
I think license exam and priority evaluation of nurses competencies in clinical environment can help reduce theory and practice gap	156	1	4	3.12	0.605
I think using what you learned in the theoretical class during the practical labs or real clinical situation will help to minimize the gap	156	1	4	3.14	0.627

Analyzed by mean (X) and Standard Deviation (SD)

Table 4 presents Pakistani nurses' perceptions of the theory-practice gap, highlighting responses on aspects like the role of respectful interpersonal relationships in clinician-academic collaboration (mean=3.14), the impact of licensing exams on reducing the gap (mean=3.12), and the value of applying theoretical knowledge in clinical practice to enhance skills and critical thinking (mean=3.14). Data from 156 participants includes each question's minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation, indicating

strong agreement that respectful collaboration and integrating theory in clinical settings can help bridge the theory-practice gap.

Questions	N	Min	Max	X	SD
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I think poor communication and collaboration between the academic areas and practical domains can cause theory practice gap	156	1	4	3.06	0.805
I think when practice in the ward the nurses do not apply all their theoretical knowledge	156	1	4	2.81	0.818
I think continuous education will help updating the nurse's knowledge about the current technological advancement can help minimize the gap	156	1	4	3.32	0.718
<i>Analyzed by mean (X) and Standard Deviation (SD)</i>					

Table 5 captures Pakistani nurses' perceptions of the theory-practice gap, with responses indicating that poor communication between academic and practical domains contributes to the gap (mean=3.06), limited application of theoretical knowledge exacerbates it (mean=2.81), and continuous education on technological advances can minimize it (mean=3.32) by enhancing critical thinking and decision-making. Data from 156 participants includes each question's minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation, highlighting nurses' belief that ongoing education is key to bridging the theory-practice gap.

Discussion: In the present study majority of participants fall within the 21-30 age range, accounting for 87.8% of the total, the study includes 5.8% males and 94.2% females. Participants were also asked about their designation, with 13.5% identifying as instructors and 86.5% as clinicians. In terms of the highest level of education, 51.3% are general nurses, 42.3% hold a Bachelor's degree, and 6.4% have a Master's degree. Participants' years of experience vary 57.1% having 4-7 years. Similarly by the report of Salah, Aljerjawy (6) showed that among nurses, most were female 57.8% ; however the with mean age of the participants were (22.32±2.65) and most of the responded were 4th year nursing students .

However, Hameed and colleague study the majority were young adults, with 67.7% aged 21-30, 25% aged 31-40, 6.8% aged 41-50, and only 0.5% above 50. The mean age was 1.40±0.640, indicating a predominantly youthful population. In terms of gender, 5.2% were male and 94.8% were female. Regarding occupation, 90.1% were Clinicians, 9.4%

were nursing Instructors. In terms of education, 47.4% had a General Nurse (RN) / Diploma, 46.4% had a Bachelor's, and 6.3% had a Master's degree. Experience-wise, 49% had 4-7 years, 30.7% had below 3 years, 13% had 8-10 years, and only 7.3% had above 10 years (12).

In the present study showed that nurses with positive perception toward theory practice gap were 94%; however, the number of nurses with negative perception were 5.8%. However by the report of Hameed and colleague show In out of 192 respondent about 65.63% fall in the poor knowledge score about theory practice gap (12).

According to the report of Shahzadi and colleague explores students' learning, implementation, differences between theory and practice, and the reasons behind such differences. Study indicate that students possess stronger theoretical knowledge compared to their practical performance. The faculty in clinical settings falls short of the required standard, contributing to the gap between theory and practice and hindering nursing students' performance. Moreover, there is a lack of integration between classroom instruction and clinical training, affecting students' self-assurance. Consequently, there is a pressing need to acknowledge the significance of bridging theory and practice and to prioritize hands-on training for nursing students. Both classroom and clinical faculty must ensure students' grasp of knowledge, practical skills, and self-assurance (13).

This present study showed that evidence-based practice will improve student's clinical judgment and invariably minimize the theory practice gap, skill laboratory will improve students confident and skill acquisition after graduation thereby minimizing the

theory practice gap and the application of the nursing process in patient care to improve critical thinking ability and clinical judgment.

According to the report of Chekerwa in 2023 the results indicated that student nurses faced challenges in participating in clinical tasks and acquiring knowledge without proper supervision and guidance. Obstacles present in both the clinical setting and among faculty hindered their ability to apply theoretical concepts to practical situations. Drawing from their encounters with these obstacles during the initial three years of study, nursing students suggested effective strategies for bridging the gap between theory and practice. Furthermore, it is emphasized that clinical supervisors and preceptors should offer support and guidance to students during their clinical placements, fostering environments that are more supportive and conducive to learning (14).

The present study analysis offers valuable insights into how Pakistani nurses perceive the relationship between theory and practice, providing a foundation for understanding their perspectives and potential areas for improvement within the profession. So the maximum nurses perceived that continuous education will help updating the nurses knowledge about the current technological advancement can help minimize the gap.

According to the report of Shqairat and colleague showed that nursing students struggle to connect what they learn in theory with what they practice in training. There are different reasons for this, like the curriculum, how they communicate, the places where they practice, their instructors, and the instructions they receive. The study suggests that nursing schools should rethink how they teach both theory and practice to help students become better nurses in the future (15). In the same context the findings of Afzal and Gilani in 2019 showed that according to the participants, the most significant challenges in the educational setting included educators sticking to traditional teaching methods in nursing care (97.1%), failure to apply theoretical aspects of the nursing process in practice (69.6%), a gap between the practice and education systems (98.1%), discrepancies between what they were taught in class and what they practiced in clinical settings (95.8%), and lack of constructive feedback from nurse

educators/clinical facilitators during supervision (96.2%) (16).

Various studies underscore the challenges faced by nursing students and professionals, including discrepancies between theoretical knowledge and practical application, inadequate supervision and guidance, and a lack of integration between classroom instruction and clinical training (17). Strategies such as continuous education, skill laboratories, and the application of evidence-based practice are suggested to bridge the theory-practice gap and improve nursing education (18). Overall, this analysis sheds light on Pakistani nurses' perceptions of the theory-practice relationship, identifying areas for improvement and emphasizing the importance of continuous education to keep pace with technological advancements and minimize the gap between theory and practice. It suggests a need for re-evaluating teaching methods and fostering supportive environments to enhance nursing education and practice.

Conclusion: The study found that most participants were aged 21-30 and predominantly female. A significant 94% of nurses held a positive perception of the theory-practice gap, suggesting that evidence-based practice, skill labs, and applying the nursing process in patient care enhance clinical judgment, confidence, and critical thinking, thus reducing the gap. Additionally, most nurses believed that continuous education on current technological advancements would further help bridge this gap, providing valuable insights for improving nursing practice in Pakistan.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullahi KO, Ghiyasvandian S, Hasanpour M. Theory-practice gap: The knowledge and perception of Nigerian nurses. *Iranian journal of nursing and midwifery research*. 2022;27(1):30.
2. D. A. Salifu JG, M. A. Salifu and J. P. Ninnoni. Experiences and perceptions of the theory-practice gap in nursing in a resource-constrained setting: A qualitative description study. *Nursing open* 2019 Vol 6 Issue 1 2019:Pages 72-83.

3. Gassas R. Sources of the knowledge-practice gap in nursing: Lessons from an integrative review. *Nurse education today*. 2021;106:105095.
4. Lee GSJ, Chin YH, Jiang AA, Mg CH, Nistala KRY, Iyer SG, et al. Teaching medical research to medical students: a systematic review. *Medical science educator*. 2021;31:945-62.
5. Akram AS, Mohamad A, Akram S. The role of clinical instructor in bridging the gap between theory and practice in nursing education. *International Journal of Caring Sciences*. 2018;11(2):876-82.
6. Salah AA, Aljerjawy M, Salama A. Gap between theory and practice in the nursing education: the role of clinical setting. *Emergency*. 2018;24(17.18).
7. Safazadeh S, Irajpour A, Alimohammadi N, Haghani F. Exploring the reasons for theory-practice gap in emergency nursing education: A qualitative research. *Journal of education and health promotion*. 2018;7.
8. Watkins A. Closing the theory-practice gap: is it possible. *star*. 2018;4:5.
9. Greenway K, Butt G, Walthall H. What is a theory-practice gap? An exploration of the concept. *Nurse education in practice*. 2019;34:1-6.
10. Masso M, Sim J, Halcomb E, Thompson C. Practice readiness of new graduate nurses and factors influencing practice readiness: A scoping review of reviews. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. 2022;129:104208.
11. Salifu DA, Gross J, Salifu MA, Ninnoni JP. Experiences and perceptions of the theory-practice gap in nursing in a resource-constrained setting: A qualitative description study. *Nursing open*. 2019;6(1):72-83.
12. Hameed A, Abdullahi KO, Yaqoob A. Knowledge of Pakistani Nurses about Theory Practice Gap in Nursing. *Pakistan Journal of Medical & Health Sciences*. 2023;17(03):40-.
13. Shahzadi C, Kousar R, Hussain M, Waqas A, Gilani SA, Safdar M. The assessment of gap between theory and training classes in nursing education system: a case of University of Lahore, Pakistan. *Saudi J Med Pharm Sci*. 2017;3(8):896-906.
14. Chekerwa P. Nursing students' perceptions of the barriers to applying theory to practice in clinical placement settings. 2023.
15. Shqairat JM, Faraj S, Sedek M. Bridge the gap between nursing theoretical education and clinical training environment in al-makassed training hospital in Palestine. 2023.
16. Afzal N, Gilani MA. Nursing Students Challenges at Educational and Clinical Environment. *Nursing*. 2019;62.
17. O'Brien AT, McNeil K, Dawson A. The student experience of clinical supervision across health disciplines—Perspectives and remedies to enhance clinical placement. *Nurse Education in Practice*. 2019;34:48-55.
18. Mbakaya BC, Kalembo FW, Zgambo M, Konyani A, Lungu F, Tveit B, et al. Nursing and midwifery students' experiences and perception of their clinical learning environment in Malawi: a mixed-method study. *BMC nursing*. 2020;19:1-14.